

IMPROVEMENT OF METHODOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF
DEVELOPING CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL
STUDENTS

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Abstract. Today, the teacher requires the use of advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in the educational process. Proceeding from the above, based on our experience, we will describe our thoughts on the ways of teaching and learning through the use of interactive techniques in the lessons. We think that it will provide practical assistance to our colleagues in increasing the effectiveness of training. It also becomes one of their close assistants in the performance of a responsible task, such as the selection of students for their direction and the formation of skills in preparation for an independent life. Below we give recommendations on the application of modern methods of teaching on the basis of some topics in the cross-section of classes.

Key words: Collaborative Activity Of The Teacher And Students, Knowledge, Skills And Skills To The Students Through Training.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДИКО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ
РАЗВИТИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ

Аннотация. Сегодня учителю требуется использование передовых педагогических и новых информационных технологий в образовательном процессе. Исходя из вышеизложенного, основываясь на нашем опыте, мы опишем наши мысли о способах преподавания и обучения за счет использования интерактивных методик на уроках. Мы думаем, что это окажет практическую помощь нашим коллегам в повышении эффективности обучения. Он также становится одним из их ближайших помощников при выполнении ответственных задач, таких как отбор студентов для их направления и формирование навыков подготовки к самостоятельной жизни. Ниже мы приводим рекомендации по применению современных методов преподавания на основе некоторых тем в разрезе занятий.

Ключевые слова: Совместная Деятельность Преподавателя И Учащихся, Передача Знаний, Умений И Навыков Учащимся Посредством Обучения.

Education is a collaborative activity of the teacher and students, in the process of which the development of the individual, his / her knowledge and upbringing are also carried out. In the lessons, the teacher achieves his knowledge, skills and skills to the students through training, while the students will have the ability to use it as a result of their assimilation. In the process of learning, students use different forms of assimilation, that is, they rely on specific discrepancies in the perception, processing and application of the assimilated information. In the educational process, issues of education and training in the form of interaction of teachers and students at the time of classes, independent performance of students, extracurricular work are solved. The purpose of education is formed in accordance with the need of society.

Therefore, the purpose of education should be appropriate and proportionate. It was noted that the purpose of education in the scientific literature is to create the right, accurate, appropriate use of the opportunities, skills and skills, develop logical and creative thinking,

increase communicative literacy, integrate the National idea, form shargona education, the expression of spiritual enrichment of a person. On the basis of educational purpose, the culture of their communication is improved by independent thinking, increasing oral and written literacy, developing logical thinking. On the basis of educational purpose, spiritual, ideological, spiritual education is provided. In the process of language learning, it becomes possible to approach the cultural and moral values of the people. One of the great wise." as long as you live with the anxiety of the future, give your children good knowledge, read". It would not be a mistake if we say that the reforms carried out in the educational system of our country in the real sense were not a work aimed at achieving efficiency in a two-year or short period, but a change in the real sense for several hundred years. This shows that the wise policy lies at the time of the idea that all the children of our country –my children, they should be stronger, educated and of course happy than us, worrying about the future of our president, our future generation. It is known that the introduction of advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in education not only increases the effectiveness of training, but also plays an important role in the upbringing of an independent and logical thinking, comprehensively high spiritual person by applying the achievements of Science in practice.

Currently, interest in the application of interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons why this happens is that by this time, in traditional education, students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, while the use of modern technologies teaches them to search for the knowledge they possess, independently study and think, analyze, and even draw the final conclusions themselves. The teacher in this process creates conditions for the development, formation, acquisition and education of the individual and at the same time performs the function of management, directing. It gives a positive result if used in the lessons of repetition or strengthening of the game-tasks in the training. The choice of what kind of a game task should depend on the type of lesson, the level at which students are taught to perform the game tasks, their level of knowledge, the possibilities of independent creative work, the ability to quickly restore the learned in memory, the extent to which creativity is also formed. In education, attention is paid to the issue of thinking the personality of the reader, understanding the thoughts of other people and teaching this idea to make literate statements in oral and written form, the main role is played by the perfection of an independent thinking, speech culture developed literate person. The lifestyle, cultural creativity of the nation is studied on the basis of its rich historical heritage.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today, the teacher requires the use of advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in the educational process. Proceeding from the above, based on our experience, we will describe our thoughts on the ways of teaching and learning through the use of interactive techniques in the lessons. We think that it will provide practical assistance to our colleagues in increasing the effectiveness of training. It also becomes one of their close assistants in the performance of a responsible task, such as the selection of students for their direction and the formation of skills in preparation for an independent life. Below we give recommendations on the application of modern methods of teaching on the basis of some topics in the cross-section of classes. You use it with a creative approach, and in response to the thoughts of our first president: "let's look for answers to the question of what we are doing today, in order to arouse

pride and pride in our children, a sense of loyalty to our sacred Mother Earth; we hope that you will add your own sense of achievement.

The use of interactive techniques and educational games, modern information and communication technologies in primary classes will help students to think independently, expand their creative search and logical thinking circles, as well as connect with life what they have learned in the lessons, increase their interest. Effective use of the conditions created on the basis of such modern requirements of teachers, organization of lessons on the basis of advanced pedagogical and Information Communication Technologies guarantees the quality of the educational process. It will give a positive result if it is used in the lessons of repetition or strengthening of the gametasks during the lessons. The choice of what kind of a game task should depend on the type of lesson, the level at which students are taught to perform the game tasks, their level of knowledge, the possibilities of independent creative work, the ability to quickly restore the learned in memory, the extent to which creativity is also formed.

In education, attention is paid to the issue of thinking the personality of the reader, understanding the thoughts of other people and teaching this idea to make literate statements in oral and written form, the main role is played by the perfection of an independent thinking, speech culture developed literate person. The lifestyle, cultural creativity of the nation is studied on the basis of its rich historical heritage.

CONCLUSION

In our opinion, the main requirements for educational games are as follows:

1. Educational games should be suitable for the age of students;
2. The games should be in proportion to the essence of the subject matter under consideration;
3. The timing of educational games must be clearly defined;
4. Educational games should have both educational and educational significance;
5. The purpose, significance of educational games should be determined.

As long as the above requirements are met, the effectiveness of the lesson will increase, and modern technologies will serve the effectiveness of Education.

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